

Document Code	EOMS-URC-FO-050, Rev. 00
Effectivity Date	2024/12/08
Page/s	Page 1 of 1

Pedagogical Planning and Practice for Indigenous Education: A Basis for an Integrated Framework for IP Education

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Abstract

Integrating Indigenous Peoples Education (IPEd) can address the call for equality and justice. A need for further study on how teachers integrate IPEd in the teaching-learning process of diverse learners is needed. This research determined the extent of IPEd integration evident in the available instructional materials of teachers of a private educational institution, as well as their thoughts in the integration process. The study made use of a modified checklist to determine the extent of IPEd integration in nine general education courses and sourced out thoughts from six instructors of the general education courses. Results reveal that across the six areas, the integration of IPEd is at the minimum. Considerable extent can be particularly be observed in materials, but remain minimal in terms of the other five areas. Indicators per area, however are varied in terms of the extent of IPEd integration. Among the instructors' responses, seven themes arose which can be connected with the six areas. It can be concluded that the findings in terms of the extent of IPEd integration may be related to distinct factors. The study suggests a crafted IPEd Integration Framework (IIF) that can be used in the general courses offered at the tertiary level.

Keywords: *evaluation of instructional materials, indigenous knowledge integration, IP education*

INTRODUCTION

The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, adopted by all members of the United Nations (Global Sustainable Development Report, 2023), highlights the urgent need to establish equality and justice by overcoming poverty and deprivation from all possible opportunities including education (par 1). The inclusion of Indigenous Peoples Education (IPEd) is one way to address the call for equality and justice (Eduardo & Gabriel, 2021). The need to understand Indigenous Peoples (IPs) or Indigenous Cultural Communities (ICCs) through formal education continues to arise. With this, integrating indigenous knowledge is the researchers' and educators' task (Paquin, 2023). The need to do so highlights the importance of allowing both IPs and non-IPs to become aware of who the IPs/ICCs are and how they are in their current situation.

The need for such understanding is influenced by the ever-changing state of IPs, including the awareness of issues that IPs/ICCs have been dealing with over time. Internationally, concerns relating to IPs/ICCs can be identified. Mullen (2021) claimed that concepts such as decolonization, self-determination, sovereignty, and futurity target the continuing plight of IPs/ICCs from a global perspective.

In the context of the Philippines, it is evident in the Department of Education's stipulation to adopt the Indigenous Peoples Education Curriculum framework, which is focused on the recognition of Indigenous peoples' right to basic education and the provision of guidance to schools in localizing, indigenizing, and enhancing the curriculum

Document Code	EOMS-URC-FO-050, Rev. 00
Effectivity Date	2024/12/08
Page/s	Page 2 of 2

(DepEd, 2015). However, studies on the extent of IPed integration are yet to be done. In addition, a definite framework does not exist in the higher education curriculum. Also, the framework of the basic education level seems to only focus more on localization and indigenization, but not necessarily on the understanding of Indigenous Knowledge, Systems, and Practices (IKSPs) per se.

The study assessed the extent of IPed integration of teachers and instructors evident in their respective instructional materials in all general education courses. The study aims to produce an Integrated Framework for IP Education as a product of the study which will serve as the basis for instructional materials revision and a sound implementation and integration of IP Education in the respective curricula of subjects and courses. The results of this study are beneficial to all teachers and administrators for them to be aware of the necessary information in the proper integration of IP Education as they do revisions in their instructional materials such as syllabi and learning materials to promote understanding of IPs and ICCs, which shall then be underscored by their teaching. It is also beneficial to future researchers who wish to venture into the importance of IP Education Integration in the curriculum.

Indigenous Peoples and Education

The community life of IPs/ICCs must be reflected in the curriculum design and framework. Also, teachers must understand the IP Education policy to help them align their methods of instruction (Villaplaza, 2021). For the understanding of IPs and ICCs to be promoted in the classroom through IPed, issues are to be addressed. Specifically, there are still educational needs to be addressed when teaching IPs. Anderson et al. (2023) concluded in their study that for schools to have IPs to excel academically, four key aspects should be honed among teachers: teachers themselves, the curriculum, pedagogy, and the school environment and culture readiness. In the Philippines, the study of Bastida et al. (2023) revealed that teachers have experienced challenges in improving the literacy skills of IP learners, such as their reading comprehension, viewing, and writing skills, despite the spiral progression of teaching classes. In addition, numerous challenges were identified by Raffoul et al. (2021) in their study: resistance of faculty and administrator due to their lack of interest and inability to understand the essence of integrating indigenization of the curriculum; lack of support, commitment, and prioritization from the administration; writing of indigenization plans alteration and few indigenous faculty and staff being hired system-wide; and heavy workload, relying on the administration to do the indigenization solely. Furthermore, it is claimed by Perez-Brito (2021) that specific data on indigenous people is lacking and needs to be collected. However, it may be challenging and it requires full attention. It is claimed by Paquin (2023) that “the integration of indigenous knowledge is a complex multifaceted issue that demands attention and action from researchers and educators” (p. 42).

Factors in building an IP Education Framework

IP Education is usually neglected in the curriculum framework of formal education. This is evident in the findings of Da Silva et al. (2023), which identified factors such as

indigenous worldview, community participation, and language ecology influence the manner an indigenous culture in school is represented; where they claim that these allow indigenous knowledge to be considered in the education system. The study also revealed that it is important to understand the local context in proposing interventions to open a possible intercultural dialogue.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1
Research Paradigm

Figure 1 presents the paradigm of the study, focusing on the extent of Indigenous Peoples Education (IPed) integration in instructional materials and the corresponding responses of instructors in using the instructional materials. The box on the left includes six areas: pedagogy and methodology, indigenous knowledge systems, curriculum content and planning, languages of instruction, materials, and assessment and evaluation. These elements are measured to see the extent how IPed is embedded within teaching materials. Concurrently, the study takes a look at the insights, practices, and challenges of instructors in employing such materials. The interaction between these two constructs informs the development of a suggested integration framework for IP Education.

Objectives of the Study

This study determined the extent of IPed integration in the instructional materials used by undergraduate general education course instructors of a private educational institution in terms of pedagogical planning and practice during the AY 2024-2025. The specific objectives are to determine the extent of IP Education integration of diagnosed instructional materials in terms of pedagogy and methodology, indigenous knowledge systems, curriculum content and planning, languages of instruction, materials, and assessment and evaluation; determine the thoughts of instructors in the integration of IPed in their courses; and suggest an IPed Integration framework for IP Education to be used on general education courses.

Document Code	EOMS-URC-FO-050, Rev. 00
Effectivity Date	2024/12/08
Page/s	Page 4 of 4

METHODOLOGY

Design

The study used both qualitative and quantitative approaches using a descriptive design. In determining the extent to which teachers' pedagogical planning and practice in integrating IPed into their curriculum and materials involved quantitative data while in terms of responses of the instructors who teach the courses where IPed is integrated, the study involved qualitative data. Both serve as the basis for the suggestion of an IP Integration Framework in the general education courses offered in higher education.

Locale, Sources of Data, and Respondents

The study was conducted at Saint Mary's University (SMU), a premier CICM Catholic educational institution. SMU is an educational institution composed of diverse cultures and ethnicities and is an institution that recognizes services to indigenous peoples. Having existing instructional materials that have incorporated IP Education and content and that have promoted inclusive education where IPs and non-IPs learn together is a suitable area to conduct the study.

The study included all nine (9) General Education Courses' (GECs) syllabi that are being used for teaching, together with their available learning materials. The study, however, excluded general elective courses in the study such as institutional courses and newly offered electives.

The study included six (6) willing GEC instructors who handle the GEC courses respectively, purposively chosen for a focus group discussion. Each instructor served as representatives of each GEC, specifically those who teach one or more GECs. They were identified based on the objectives of the study through non-probability sampling (Hassan, 2024).

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

The study included completely written syllabi and learning materials. In terms of the respondents, the study included full-time teachers who may be categorized as part-time temporary (PT-T), probationary (PR), and/or regular instructors who teach the GEC regularly as their primary purpose in the institution is to teach.

The study did not include guest lecturers teaching the GECs, as well as part-time teachers, and administrators who have teaching loads since their focus on the subject may not be as precise as that of full-time teachers.

Research Instruments

The study used a checklist in the study of Villaplaza (2021), modified to determine the extent of IP Education Integration of teachers in their respective instructional materials. The modifications included contextualizing items based on the grade level, course, subject nature, and the kind of material, as well as removing items that may not be necessary for the study. The checklist will include items for each area: Pedagogy and Methodology, Indigenous Knowledge Systems, Curriculum Content and Planning, Languages of Instruction, Materials, and Assessment and Evaluation. Teacher training

Document Code	EOMS-URC-FO-050, Rev. 00
Effectivity Date	2024/12/08
Page/s	Page 5 of 5

shall be excluded because the study focuses only on the instructional materials. A four-point scale (from no indication of integration to a great extent) was used to determine the extent. In terms of the focus group discussion, the questions include one for each area aforementioned. The focus group discussion was done in the mode of writing due to the unavailability of every respondent to be together in one meeting.

Data Gathering Procedure

The data-gathering procedure underwent four steps within the academic year 2024-2025. The informed consent form (ICF) shall be given to all target respondents of the study. The ICF shall be read carefully by the respondents, and upon their approval, the data collection shall start with the collation of instructional materials. The different instructional materials were collected on December 02, 2024. Only the soft copies were requested and collated in one Google Drive (GDrive) link. They were sorted according to its material type: syllabus or learning material. The sources were then reviewed by the group of assessors, composed of the researchers and three (3) experts identified whose expertise included language, and curriculum and instruction. The group of assessors were composed of three IPs and four non-IPs. A consensus meeting was conducted to have one final assessment of the extent. Upon review by the group, the results were then presented to the respondents for verification. Individually, the instructors agreed with the results.

A modified focus group discussion was conducted through which the respondents gave their responses in written form. This is due to the reason that the respondents were not available in the multiple attempts of a meeting to happen. Their responses were then collected and verified upon receiving their answers.

Treatment of Data/Data Analysis

The scores were represented with mean scores. Each mean score shall be classified according to a verbal description. The following are the intervals used in the study: 0.00 (No Indication of Integration); 0.01-1.99 (Minimal Extent); 2.00-2.99 (Considerable Extent); and 3.00-3.99 (Great Extent). The data from the focus group discussion were treated thematically, which served as basis in crafting the suggested framework.

Ethical Considerations

This study underwent ethical review in the Saint Mary's University Research Ethics Board (SMUREB). Data collected were objectively conducted by both internal researchers and external researchers who are not affiliated with SMU. The informed consent process was also clearly outlined the researcher's affiliation and ensure voluntary participation. This study made assurance to the respondents that all information obtained, including names, will be kept confidential and anonymous. All data were coded using unique identifiers to protect respondent privacy further. The study has various benefits for the respondents, outweighing possible risks.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Section 1. Extent of IPed Integration in General Education Courses

Table 1

Extent of IPed Integration in General Education Courses (GECs) in terms of the Six Areas

	GEC1	GEC2	GE3	GEC4	GEC5	GEC6	GEC7	GEC8	GEC9	Overall	QD
Pedagogy and Methodology	1.18	0.82	1.36	1.64	1.55	1.82	0.64	1.18	1.27	1.27	ME
Indigenous Knowledge Systems	1.00	0.67	0.67	1.17	0.83	1.33	1.00	0.33	0.33	0.81	ME
Curriculum Content and Planning	1.60	0.70	1.70	1.90	1.60	1.70	0.80	0.80	1.70	1.39	ME
Languages of Instruction	1.17	0.67	0.67	1.50	1.50	2.17	1.33	1.00	0.83	1.20	ME
Materials	2.40	1.80	2.20	2.20	2.40	2.60	1.80	1.80	1.40	2.07	CE
Assessment and Evaluation	0.94	0.81	0.94	1.00	1.13	1.31	0.63	0.63	0.63	0.89	ME
Overall Extent	1.38	0.91	1.26	1.57	1.50	1.82	1.03	0.96	1.03	1.27	ME

Legend: 0.00 (NI: No Indication of Integration); 0.01-1.99 (ME: Minimal Extent); 2.00-2.99 (CE: Considerable Extent); and 3.00 (GE: Great Extent)

Table 1 shows that the overall extent of IPed integration in General Education Courses (GECs) is at a *minimal extent* (M=1.27). Among the six areas, *Materials* recorded the highest integration (M=2.07, CE), while *Indigenous Knowledge Systems* had the lowest (M=0.81, ME). It can also be observed that GEC6 consistently shows higher integration, while GEC8 reflects the least. This may mean that although materials reflect some level of integration, fundamental aspects of IPED remain lacking across the subjects. This emphasizes that there is yet a need to improve the integration of IPed in the general education courses.

Table 2

Extent of IPed Integration in General Education Courses (GECs) in terms of Pedagogy and Methodology

Pedagogy and Methodology	Mean	SD	QD
1. Education is seen as connected to all aspects of life and the well-being of both IP and Non-IP learners.	2.44	0.73	CE
2. Education is seen as connected to the environment.	2.11	1.17	CE
3. The situation of indigenous communities is the starting point in developing the potential of learners.	1.11	0.78	ME
4. The situation of indigenous communities is the starting point in developing their own views, values, priorities, and aspirations.	1.11	0.6	ME
5. Indigenous community members, parents, and elders are consulted and involved regarding what their students should, and want to learn – and when and how – as a basis for identifying pedagogical principles.	0	0	NI
6. Indigenous community members, parents and elders are consulted and involved regarding what their pupils should learn – and when and how – as the basis for identifying teaching methods at the start of the program.	0	0	NI
7. Both formal and non-formal, as well as traditional and modern, teaching methods are used, based on the study of traditional teaching methods at home	0.78	0.67	ME
8. Both formal and non-formal, as well as traditional and modern, teaching methods are used, based on the study, of traditional teaching methods in the community like excursions to learn about the cultural significance of places	0.56	0.53	ME
9. Both formal and non-formal, as well as traditional and modern, teaching methods are used, based on the study, of traditional teaching methods in participation in ceremonies with family	0.78	0.67	ME

members to learn about rituals associated songs, dances, astrological observations, etc.

10. A cooperative, interactive and reflexive teaching-learning process is promoted, based on all aspects of knowledge.	2.67	0.5	CE
11. A co-operative, interactive and reflexive teaching-learning process is promoted, based on the experience of learners.	2.44	0.53	CE

Legend: 0.00 (NI: No Indication of Integration); 0.01-1.99 (ME: Minimal Extent); 2.00-2.99 (CE: Considerable Extent); and 3.00 (GE: Great Extent)

Table 2 shows that there a *minimal extent* of IPEd integration in pedagogy and methodology (overall M=1.27, ME). Though some indicators like the promotion of interactive, reflexive teaching-learning processes (Items 10 & 11, M=2.67 and 2.44, CE respectively) present a high integration, most indicators fall under the minimal range, with two items showing *no indication* (Items 5 & 6, M=0.00, NI). This may be due to the reason that while general pedagogical values aligned with IPEd are in a way practiced as evident in the instructional materials, grounded methods relating to IPEd such as community-based input and traditional knowledge systems are may not be used or may be absent. This reveals a gap between theoretical alignment with IPEd principles and practical implementation.

Table 3

Extent of IPEd Integration in General Education Courses (GECs) in terms of Indigenous Knowledge Systems

Indigenous Knowledge Systems	Mean	SD	QD
1. Respect for, and recognition of ownership of indigenous communities as holders of indigenous knowledge	1.56	0.73	ME
2. Respect for and recognition of ownership of indigenous communities as holders for their specific ways of generating and transmitting knowledge.	1.67	0.71	ME
3. Stories, diaries, textbooks, etc., are produced by indigenous teachers.	0.56	0.73	ME
4. Non-verbal education materials are produced by indigenous teachers.	0.56	0.73	ME
5. The active participation of students and community members who serve to develop a curriculum founded on indigenous people's cultural identity.	0.11	0.33	ME
6. The active participation of students and community members who serve to develop a curriculum founded on indigenous people's cultural history.	0.44	0.53	ME

Legend: 0.00 (NI: No Indication of Integration); 0.01-1.99 (ME: Minimal Extent); 2.00-2.99 (CE: Considerable Extent); and 3.00 (GE: Great Extent)

Table 3 shows that all indicators are rated within *minimal extent* (ME) (M=0.11-1.67), with particularly low means in curriculum development with the involvement of the community (M=0.11-0.44). Although there might be evidence of paying respect to indigenous knowledge holders (M=1.56-1.67), explicit inclusion in materials and curricula is limited to none. This suggests that despite the existence of the acknowledgment of such systems, the integration is rather implied/symbolic than explicit/meaningful approach.

Table 4

Extent of IPEd Integration in General Education Courses (GECs) in terms of Curriculum Content and Planning

Curriculum Content and Planning	Mean	SD	QD
1. Are designed with the active involvement of indigenous communities	0	0	NI
2. Gradually integrate indigenous and Western forms of knowledge	1.33	0.87	ME
3. Gradually integrate indigenous and Western ways of knowing	1.33	0.87	ME
4. Are place-and culture-based	1.33	0.87	ME
5. Include seasonal-environmental curricula	1.22	0.97	ME
6. Include the use of local flora	0.78	0.67	ME
7. Include the use of local fauna	0.78	0.67	ME
8. Reflect the interrelation of subjects	2.56	0.53	CE
9. Also promote positive attitudes to indigenous languages to promote understanding tolerance and solidarity between different cultural groups.	2.33	0.87	CE
10. Also promote positive attitudes to indigenous cultures among the non-indigenous population, to promote understanding, tolerance and solidarity between different cultural groups.	2.22	0.83	CE

Legend: 0.00 (NI: No Indication of Integration); 0.01-1.99 (ME: Minimal Extent); 2.00-2.99 (CE: Considerable Extent); and 3.00 (GE: Great Extent)

Table 4 reveals that most indicators fall within *minimal extent* (ME) range, with a few reaching *considerable extent* (CE), such as cultural responsiveness in teaching practices (M=2.56). However, some areas show *no integration* (NI), particularly in teaching methods involving community input. This suggests that while efforts to incorporate IPEd in the curriculum, they remain inconsistent and lack deeper and explicit emphasis of community-based engagement in competencies, objectives, methodologies, and the other facets. There is a need to enhance these areas and state the integration explicitly.

Table 5
Extent of IPEd Integration in General Education Courses (GECs) in terms of Language and Instruction

Languages and Instruction	Mean	SD	QD
1. Recognizing that language is not only a tool for communication and knowledge but also a fundamental element of cultural identity	1.67	0.71	ME
2. Teaching and learning indigenous knowledge and curricula through indigenous language and produced material in indigenous languages.	1.11	0.33	ME
3. Teaching and learning indigenous knowledge and curricula through the use of locally researched and produced material in indigenous languages	0.89	0.6	ME
4. Teaching and learning of and through the mother tongue moving on to learning other languages in a culturally appropriate and gradual way, according to learners' capacities and needs.	1.33	0.71	ME
5. Involving native speakers of indigenous languages as teachers.	1	0.5	ME
6. Learning other languages as a basis for cross-cultural understanding and tolerance	1.22	0.97	ME

Legend: 0.00 (NI: No Indication of Integration); 0.01-1.99 (ME: Minimal Extent); 2.00-2.99 (CE: Considerable Extent); and 3.00 (GE: Great Extent)

Table 5 indicates that all indicators are rated with *minimal extent* (ME) (M=0.89–1.67), highlighting weak integration of indigenous languages in instruction. Particularly low scores in using indigenous-produced materials (M=0.89) and speakers of native languages as teachers (M=1.0) reflect limited practical implementation.

Instructional practices lack inclusivity of other languages (particularly the indigenous/native ones), stressing a gap.

Table 6
Extent of IPed Integration in General Education Courses (GECs) in terms of Materials

Materials	Mean	SD	QD
1. Material based on respect for the cultural values and specific relationship with natural of indigenous communities	2	0.87	CE
2. Visual, sensory and practical materials for non-verbal communication	2.33	0.5	CE
3. Material in indigenous languages and incorporating indigenous knowledge produced with the participation and consent of indigenous communities, teachers and learners.	0.89	0.78	ME
4. Material that promotes an interactive teaching-learning process.	3	0	GE
5. Material that provides an accurate picture and fair information on indigenous cultures and ways of life.	2.11	0.6	CE

Legend: 0.00 (NI: No Indication of Integration); 0.01-1.99 (ME: Minimal Extent); 2.00-2.99 (CE: Considerable Extent); and 3.00 (GE: Great Extent)

Table 6 shows a *considerable extent* overall (M=0.89–3.00). The highest-rated item involves interactive learning materials (M=3.00, GE), highlighting strong support for engaging pedagogical practices. However, materials in indigenous languages and knowledge scored the lowest (M=0.89, ME), showing minimal localization. This highlights a preference for globally accessible resources over local and/or community-specific resources, which may be due to the lack of resources or expertise in material production for IP learning. It underscores the need for co-creation with indigenous communities to ensure authenticity, as well as policy reinforcement to support resource allocation and training.

Table 7
Extent of IPed Integration in General Education Courses (GECs) in terms of Assessment and Evaluation

Assessment and Evaluation	Mean	SD	QD
Learning outcomes (in terms of students' cultural knowledge, practical skills and understanding and their ability to use these in different contexts): through observation, practical assessment, linking students' performance at home with that in school, standardized and norm-based tests when and where appropriate.	2.33	0.71	CE
Teaching methods and practices (in terms of cultural responsiveness and effectiveness in promoting students' growth, vis-à-vis the national curriculum through self-assessment.	2.56	0.53	CE
Teaching methods and practices (in terms of cultural responsiveness and effectiveness in promoting students' growth, vis-à-vis the national curriculum through participatory research by educators	0.56	0.53	ME
Teaching methods and practices (in terms of cultural responsiveness and effectiveness in promoting students' growth, vis-à-vis the national curriculum through observation and review by elders and parents.	0	0	NI
Teaching methods and practices (in terms of cultural responsiveness and effectiveness in promoting students' growth, vis-à-vis the national curriculum through observation and review by parents	0	0	NI
Teaching methods and practices (in terms of cultural responsiveness and effectiveness in promoting students' growth, vis-à-vis the national curriculum through interviewing students	1	0	NI
Teaching methods and practices (in terms of cultural responsiveness and effectiveness in	1.78	0.83	ME

promoting students' growth, vis-à-vis the national curriculum through comparing their learning activities in school

Teachers' performance (in terms of their ability to utilize different instruction strategies and to provide multiple learning opportunities for students, as well as their competence in regard local and national languages and their cultural knowledge): through self-assessment.	1.78	0.83	ME
Teachers' performance (in terms of their ability to utilize different instruction strategies and to provide multiple learning opportunities for students, as well as their competence in regard local and national languages and their cultural knowledge): through participatory research by teachers themselves.	1.11	0.93	ME
Teachers' performance (in terms of their ability to utilize different instruction strategies and to provide multiple learning opportunities for students, as well as their competence in regard local and national languages and their cultural knowledge): through the provision of opportunities for teachers to expand their pedagogical skills.	0.67	0.71	ME
Curriculum (in terms of content, priorities, timing and the interrelation of subjects based on national as well as cultural standards): through continuous review and redefinition by all educational actors.	0.89	0.6	ME
Materials (in terms of their accuracy and appropriateness, in relation to the local cultural context and natural environment): through establishing of review committees in the creation and review of textbooks and other curriculum materials.	0.33	0.71	ME
Materials (in terms of their accuracy and appropriateness in relation to the local cultural context and natural environment): using multiple levels and perspectives in the creation and review of textbooks and other curriculum materials.	0.33	0.71	ME
Programs as a whole (in terms of the incorporation of indigenous culture and language): through meetings.	0.11	0.33	ME
Programs as a whole (in terms of the incorporation of indigenous culture and language): through committees.	0.11	0.33	ME
Programs as a whole (in terms of the incorporation of indigenous culture and language): through informal events to plan, review, and redefine programs.	0.67	0.71	ME

Legend: 0.00 (NI: No Indication of Integration); 0.01-1.99 (ME: Minimal Extent); 2.00-2.99 (CE: Considerable Extent); and 3.00 (GE: Great Extent)

Table 7 shows that in terms of assessment and evaluation, integration is at a *minimal to considerable extent* (M=0.11–2.56). The highest-rated item is the use of culturally responsive assessment practices (M=2.56, CE), indicating a moderate but promising integration. Conversely, many items received a mean of 1.00 or lower, particularly those involving interviewing elders and language-based performance tasks, reflecting *no indication* or *minimal extent* of integration. This suggests that although there are efforts integrate indigenous viewpoints in assessment methods, traditional tools still dominate the lessons, addressing students in a general sense.

Section 2. Thoughts of Instructors in IPed Integration

Seven themes were derived from the qualitative responses of the instructors handling GECs when asked on how they integrate IPed in their instructional materials, together with issues that they themselves also mentioned with regard to their manner of integration:

Meaningful Learning through Contextualized Experiential Learning

Culturally relevant and experiential pedagogy is a must in the teaching of students. In other words, IPed is integrated through real-life scenarios and connected with the immediate context of the community:

Document Code	EOMS-URC-FO-050, Rev. 00
Effectivity Date	2024/12/08
Page/s	Page 11 of 11

I use IPed to teach Art Appreciation through incorporating real-life scenarios in our discussions. I always make sure that we connect art to life, the environment, and the community, which allows my students to develop a better understanding of the topics by allowing them to share their everyday experiences (Respondent 1).

Similarly, teachers mentioned classroom activities where students are active participants of the lesson by experiencing what they need to learn:

...part of our lesson includes how the student is a member of their community, letting them be a part of the learning process rather than through lectures. For example, I have all the students who are willing to share, answer questions related to the topic of the day (Respondent 5).

Limited Knowledge and Engagement with IKSPs

Understanding of teachers of the different Indigenous Knowledge, Systems, and Practices (IKSPs) of different IP groups can be crucial in the learning process. Teachers recognize the value of IKSPs through sharing of student input, but at the same time recognize the limited collaboration with Indigenous communities due to challenges in identifying in an actual setting: "In terms of community involvement in education planning, there is no involvement due to the lack of time for consultation and at the same time, there's a bit of difficulty in identifying the appropriate personalities for consultation" (Respondent 2).

Glocal Knowledge for Course Content

A blend global and local knowledge is important in the development of course content outlines, where IPed can be integrated. There are mentions of the need to contextualize and localize abstract global concepts for better student comprehension:

...there is a blending of local and global knowledge so as to contextualize and localize the lessons for the students to be able to see the interconnectedness of global concepts and their relationship with the local concepts. Also, it helps the students comprehend the lessons better since it is not only anchored on the global scale but most importantly, they are able to see its significance when related to their local context (respondent 3).

Language as a Medium for Inclusion and Identity

Language serves as not only a tool for education but as a bridge for inclusion and identity in understanding IPs and non-IPs as part of the community. There is an emphasis to the need for understanding of languages in order to understand other cultures:

Language involves communication. There is a term called intercultural communication. Intercultural communication serves as a bridge in filling in the gap between two different cultures. This can serve as a basis in bridging IP Education as well (respondent 6).

Teachers also allow the use of native languages in oral interactions, especially for those with difficulty sharing information through English and/or Tagalog, but also

Document Code	EOMS-URC-FO-050, Rev. 00
Effectivity Date	2024/12/08
Page/s	Page 12 of 12

mentions that there some students who feel “ashamed” to use their own language publicly. In contrast, some restricts written outputs to English and Filipino but permits students to speak in their preferred language during discussions, recognizing its role in fostering comfort and inclusivity, which showcases teacher’s attitude of a language as a factor on why there is minimal extent in indigenous language use in instruction.

Lack of Teacher Preparation and Training

Insufficient training in IPEd-specific methodologies is also mentioned by the respondents. None of the participants considered themselves well-trained in indigenous education. some teachers would even argue that the subject assigned to them may not be suitable for IPEd integration: *“Iba kasi ang atake sa subject na yun. Parang imposibleng mag-IPEd doon kasi puro readings at science talaga.”* [The subject has a different attack. It seems impossible to integrate IPEd there since it is mostly reading and pure science.] Participant 2 also claimed: “IPEd is not just a piece of cake,” emphasizing the need for consistent and meaningful teacher capacitation

Enhancement of Instructional Materials

Refinement of instructional materials should include IPEd integration. A respondent mentioned efforts to develop authentic materials, but nonetheless, acknowledges the need for further enhancement in the aspect of IPEd integration:

Some of the materials I use do honor indigenous culture, but I know there’s still room for improvement. I include visuals, readings, and videos that show local art and indigenous traditions. I try to make sure they are accurate and respectful not just taken from random sources online. I also encourage my students to do research from real communities or interview elders if they can. However, most of the materials are still in Filipino or English. I haven’t had the chance to use materials in local Indigenous languages, mostly because they’re not easily available. I also wish there were more interactive materials created with Indigenous communities — not just about them (respondent 1).

Culturally Responsive Assessment Tools

There is a need for creative ways of conducting authentic assessments or use assessment tools that are culturally responsive. Respondent 5 suggested incorporating activities that involve community engagement can be done for better learning and testing of learning: “...there can be an activity where students would interview an elder of their culture, to learn about the origins of a certain ritual.”

Section 3. Suggested IPEd Integration Framework

With the results presented, a framework was crafted by synthesizing the areas identified by Villaplaza (2021) and themes derived from the responses. This is suggested to address gaps identified when integrating IPEd. This integration framework aims to address the different areas and their respective indicators, especially the ones that were

rated with no indication and/or minimal extent. Based on the responses of the respondents, practical recommendations to improve IPed integration were also considered: need for community-based teacher training; the co-creation of culturally sensitive materials; and the inclusion of local voices in the classroom; developing classroom activities tailored to IPed; curriculum shift to include IPs/ICCs terminologies in the discussions.

Figure 2
Suggested IP Integration Framework

Figure 2 emphasizes that the extent of IPed integration relies on the teachers' readiness and character of being equipped with the necessary facets in integrating IPed in their respective GECs. This must be done carefully and properly before a proper integration of IPed in the instructional materials that they use in teaching. The use of this approach will not only be beneficial to learners, but also relevant in the institutionalization of IPed integration in the higher education. This is anchored by the study of Miole (2024) where she mentioned the statement: "...institutionalizing cultural interface requires interplaying Indigenous learning systems and national education systems through a rights-based partnership between Indigenous communities and relevant institutions" (p. 290).

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study concludes that due to the minimal extent of IPed integration as observed in the instructional materials of general education courses or GECs, multiple areas and indicators are yet to be addressed by the GEC instructors. Considering how the responses

Document Code	EOMS-URC-FO-050, Rev. 00
Effectivity Date	2024/12/08
Page/s	Page 14 of 14

were given, it can be concluded that the respondents themselves unknowingly verify the importance of the six areas in the preparation for IPed integration or in the planning phase. There is a need for teachers to review their instructional materials, especially that they deal with both IPs and non-IPs in the teaching-learning process. The framework suggested is basically supported by the results of this study, which the study recommends for use and/or consideration in improving the integration of IPed in the higher level of learning.

References

- Anderson, P. J., Yip, S. Y., & Diamond, Z. M. (2023) Getting schools ready for Indigenous academic achievement: a meta-synthesis of the issues and challenges in Australian schools, *International Studies in Sociology of Education*, 32:4, 1152-1175, 10.1080/09620214.2021.2025142
- Bastida, E. L., Saysi, J. G., & Batuctoc, L. V. M. (2023). Pedagogical struggles and gaps in language literacy enhancement: the case of indigenous people's education teachers in the Philippines. *International Journal of Curriculum and Instruction*, 15(1) (2022) 142-165
- Da Silva, C., Pereira, F., & Amorim, J. P. (2023). The integration of indigenous knowledge in school: a systematic review. *Compare: A Journal of Comparative and International Education*, 1-19. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03057925.2023.2184200>
- Department of Education (2015). DO 32, S. 2015 – Adopting the indigenous peoples' education curriculum framework. https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2015/07/DO_s2015_32.pdf
- Eduardo, J.P. & Gabriel, A.G. (2021). Indigenous Peoples and the Right to Education: The Dumagat Experience in the Provinces of Nueva Ecija and Aurora, in the Philippines. *SAGE*, 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440211009491>
- Kapur, R. (2019). Development of teaching-learning materials. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/334083571_Development_of_Teaching-Learning_Materials
- Hassan, M. (2024). Purposive sampling – Methods, types and examples. Retrieved from: <https://researchmethod.net/purposive-sampling/>
- IPRA (Republic Act No. 8371). 1997. "The Indigenous Peoples Rights Act of 1997." 29 October 1997. <http://ncipcar.ph/images/pdfs/IPRA.pdf>
- Miole, G. L. (2024). Cultural interface in action: A case study of Philippine indigenous educational policy, *IAFOR Journal of Education*, 12(3), 273-298. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1453359.pdf>
- Mullen, C. A. (2021). Educational issues of indigenous peoples: past, present, and future snapshots. *The Palgrave Handbook of Educational Leadership and Management Discourse*. Palgrave Macmillan, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-39666-4_89-1
- Murphy, R. (2018). The concept of syllabus design and curriculum development: a look at five major syllabus designs.

Document Code	EOMS-URC-FO-050, Rev. 00
Effectivity Date	2024/12/08
Page/s	Page 15 of 15

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/322852723_The_Concept_of_Syllabus_Design_and_Curriculum_Development_A_Look_at_Five_Major_Syllabus_Designs
National Coalition on Indigenous Peoples (2012). NCIP Administrative Order No. 1 Series of 2012. <http://ncipcar.ph/images/pdfs/ncip-ao-no-1-s-2012-iksp.pdf>
Paquin, A. (2023). The integration of indigenous knowledge in education. *Literature Reviews*, 18. https://digitalcommons.tacoma.uw.edu/med_theses/18
Perez-Brito, C. (2021). No data, no story: What the absence of Indigenous Peoples-specific data reveals. <https://blogs.worldbank.org/en/opendata/no-data-no-story-what-absence-indigenous-peoples-specific-data-reveals>
Raffoul, J., Kecheho, J., & Kustra, E. (2021). Indigenizing the curriculum: from challenges to opportunities. Retrieved from <https://scholar.uwindsor.ca/research-result-summaries/117>
UN (2023). *Global Sustainable Development Report, 2023*. <https://sdgs.un.org/goals>
UNDP (2016) Annual Report on The Rule of Law and Human Rights: For Sustaining Peace and Fostering Development: https://www.undp.org/content/undp/en/home/librarypage/democratic-governance/access_to_justiceandruloflaw/rule-of-law-annual-report-2016.html
United Nations (2018) *United nations declaration on the rights of indigenous peoples*. www.un.org
Villaplaza, L. B. (2021). Level of implementation of indigenous people's education program in Agusan Del Sur, Philippines. *Asia Pacific Journal of Contemporary Education and Communication Technology (APJCECT)*, 7(1). https://apiar.org.au/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/3_APJCECT_V7I1_pp20-33.pdf